

From bias to breakthrough: a guide to sex and gender in biomedical research

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Abstract

Basic and translational biomedical research studies biological processes involved in human and animal development in health and disease, starting from the level of single molecules, cells, and tissues to the system-level approaches that integrate complex functions. Historically, however, it has been male-centric, omitting to acknowledge and study the differences between males and females. This has led not only to missed opportunities for scientific discovery but to the dire consequences of misdiagnoses, failed clinical trials and inappropriate therapies for both sexes. While researchers are becoming increasingly aware of the concepts of sex and gender and their influence on human health and disease, they still lack accessible resources with clear definitions and instructions for the incorporation of sex and gender as variables at the level of basic and translational biomedical research. With this structured overview of each stage of the biomedical research process we will encourage scientists to translate conceptual insights into actionable steps—from hypothesis formulation to data reporting—aiming to improve the rigor, reproducibility, and effectiveness of biomedical research.

1. Introduction

Ideas and concepts developed by biomedical researchers help shape our understanding of health and disease and can translate into potential therapies and treatments. Biomedical research investigates mechanisms that underlie the development and function of all living organisms, starting from the level of single molecules, cells, and tissues to the system-level approaches that integrate complex functions (National Research Council (US) Committee for Monitoring the Nation's Changing Needs for Biomedical 2005; Anjum, Copeland, and Rocca 2020). While the basic biomedical research unravels how living organisms develop and function, translational biomedical research moves scientific discoveries towards application in human health and includes preclinical and animal studies, ultimately leading to clinical biomedical research – testing in human clinical trials with the end goal of novel therapeutic solutions and diagnostic options.

Human development and physiology differ between males and females, and the disease and response to therapy manifest differently in the two sexes. In clinical biomedical research, and to some extent in translational research with *ex vivo* models derived from patients/human tissue, gender also plays a role (Springer, Mager Stellman, and Jordan-Young 2012; Mauvais-Jarvis et al. 2020). However, to date, many biomedical scientists do not take into consideration the roles sex and gender have in human health and are unintentionally omitting them in the research design and data interpretation. Despite being voiced out a decade ago (Ritz et al. 2014), steps for the incorporation of sex and gender into experimental approaches are not universally followed. The Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) guidelines have attempted to provide a framework for improved reporting of sex and gender in scientific publications across disciplines (Leopold et al. 2014; Heidari et al. 2016), but these guidelines have not yet become requirements for publication.

As researchers, we all have a responsibility for addressing the problem of sex bias and sex omission. Providing open resources on how to incorporate the sex and gender dimension in biomedical research is especially important in light of the recent decisions

of the USA government, which made inaccessible research and training resources from the National Institutes of Health regarding these topics. This piece will provide the basic definitions and instructions for the incorporation of sex, and gender where possible, at the level of basic and translational biomedical research. We hope that this piece will encourage scientists to consider sex and gender as variables in biomedical research where it is deemed relevant.

2. Sex and gender defined from a biomedical perspective

Humans reproduce sexually. For a successful reproduction, haploid gametes (X and Y) from a genetic male (XY) and genetic female (XX) fuse to form a diploid zygote. In biomedical science, sex refers to the biological and physiological attributes that differ between male and female individuals (Schiebinger 2020). Sex chromosomes, sex hormones and reproductive organs (gonads, internal and external genitals) are biological determinants of sex. At the genetic level, every cell in the human body has a defined sex (Bradbury 2023). Although there are exceptional examples of chimerism (having present both XY and XX cells in the body), the binary distinction is important for addressing the basic questions of the human biology.

The binary distinction does not negate that intersex individuals with variations in number of sex chromosomes exist (Turner syndrome (X), Klinefelter syndrome (XXY) and XYY or XXXY syndromes), or variation in the external genitalia, presence or absence of the gonads (testes or ovaries), internal reproductive organs, and varied levels of hormone production and hormone responsiveness. However, the intricate process of sex determination with many gene networks, where sex chromosomes determine the sexual differentiation of gonads and the expression of sex steroid hormones, gives rise to the two sexes. Individuals in whom the anatomic sex is at odds with their chromosomal or gonadal sex are rare — about 1 in 4,500 people. Sex-chromosome aneuploidies (XO, XXX, XXY, XYY, and XXYY) are conditions with abnormal number of chromosomes (Le Gall et al. 2017), and individuals carrying these genotypes have characteristic physical and neurologic profiles (Skuse, Printzlau, and Wolstencroft 2018) and most commonly have impaired infertility. For the basic biomedical research, the distinction typically drawn

between the females and males at XX and XY genotype of the cell is important, as these chromosomes dictate key developmental gene networks.

Impact of sex on human body changes over the lifetime, is dynamic and demands an integrative approach (McCullough, McCarthy, and de Vries 2014). Sexually dimorphic (distinct, non-overlapping) anatomical features in humans include gonads, internal and external genitals, and fully differentiated breasts, while a plethora of other sex differences exist on a spectrum (overlapping but shifted distributions) (Figure 1).

dimorphic

overlapping

Figure 1. Examples of dimorphic and overlapping sex differences. Sexually dimorphic (distinct, non-overlapping) features in humans are shown in the upper panel and sex differences with overlapping but shifted distributions are shown in the lower panel. Shades of pink and blue represent female- and male-

derived DNA, sex chromosomes, cells and organs, respectively. Figure generated with vectors from NIAID NIH Bio Art source. (<https://bioart.niaid.nih.gov/> downloaded on 18th July 2025).

Body composition (percent of fat and muscle), metabolism, neurological processes, hormonal status, immunity and pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of drugs differ between the sexes. The incidence, prevalence, and severity of the disease may also differ between the sexes, as may the response to the treatment. Investigating biological phenomena in only one sex hinders our ability to prevent and treat diseases, while mechanisms underlying sex differences remain poorly understood (Mauvais-Jarvis et al. 2020).

Unfortunately, many biomedical researchers are still unfamiliar with the distinction between the sex and the gender or use the terms interchangeably. Gender refers to the sociocultural attitudes, identities and behaviors, and varies from society to society; changes with place and time, can intersect with sex, but also with age, ethnicity, socioeconomic status and sexual orientation (Schiebinger 2020). Gender is unique to humans, can only be studied in humans and cannot be appropriately modeled in animal models (Savic, Garcia-Falgueras, and Swaab 2010). The term gender cannot be applied to animals, as we cannot know whether animals have perception of their sex (McCarthy 2015). Only certain aspects of the plethora of gender variables can be modeled. In this manuscript terms male and female will refer to the biological sex, and terms woman and man will refer to the gender.

Both sex and gender have important effects on human biology and health, but effects of neither have to be fixed or determined. In animals, including humans, processes that occur during sexual differentiation are determined by the complex gene networks and molecular pathways, and not by single genes. Sex impacts social practices of the gender, but the environment and the experiences through various mechanisms including epigenetic, endocrine and neurological can also influence aspects of the sexual differentiation during the human lifespan (Fausto-Sterling 2019). Gendered behaviors and experiences intersect with sex. Examples of sex and gender differences are given in the Table 1. The juxtaposition in the table conveys that a comprehensive study of human

development and diseases of the human organism always requires consideration of both the sex and the gender perspective.

SEX differences (biological)	GENDER differences (sociocultural)
Chromosomal differences (XX vs. XY)	Gender assignment and identity development
Sex hormone levels (e.g., estrogen/testosterone)	Gendered expectations of emotional expression
Reproductive anatomy (e.g., uterus, testes)	Norms about reproduction and caregiving roles
Muscle mass and fat distribution	Expectations in physical activity and body image
Immune system response	Health-seeking behaviour and access to care
Brain structure and neurochemistry	Socialization in education and occupation choices
Cardiovascular physiology	Stress exposure by role strain or discrimination
Metabolic rate and drug metabolism	Prescribing biases and adherence to treatment
Pain perception and sensitivity	Expression and reporting of pain

Table 1. Exemplary sex and gender differences.

3. How to incorporate sex into the experimental design

In many human diseases, including cardiovascular, neurological and cancer, differences between the male and female patients exist in nearly every aspect, from epidemiology to the outcome. While women are now included as roughly a half of all participants in clinical trials, due to the implementation of policies on inclusion of women in clinical research (National Institutes of Health (U.S.) and National Institutes of Health (U.S.). Office of Extramural Research. 2001), more often than not basic and preclinical biomedical research have focused on male animals and cells. Sex differences arise from a combination of genetic, epigenetic (DNA methylation, histone modification, chromatin remodeling), hormonal and environmental factors (including behavior and lifestyle). Sex is a key biological variable and even when the sex differences are not the subject of the study, both male and female cells and tissues derived from animals or humans should be included in the experimental design. Any biological material derived from patients will have sex and age as two key interacting variables.

The influence of sex on a biological process changes with age, as there are critical points during the human and animal development in which hormone fluctuations have significant impact. For example, most recently it has been shown that androgen-driven thymus atrophy in males (in both humans and mice) results in significant sex differences in immunity during middle age, which translates to lower protection against infection and cancer in males (Menzel et al. 2025).

While studying sex differences does pose a challenge of adequate sample size for a well-powered analysis (Khramtsova, Davis, and Stranger 2019), and there have been suggestions to study sex differences as continuous variables (Yang and Rubin 2024), appropriate analysis and reporting of data by sex will enhance the rigor and applicability of preclinical biomedical research (NIH 2024). Regardless of the approach, the first step in planning of the study, after formulation of the hypothesis, is to get acquainted with the state-of-the-art: whether it has already been reported that the phenomenon under the study had a different incidence or prevalence based on the sex or gender, and what has been reported about sex or gender differences or sex-related mechanisms and gender influenced factors related to the phenomenon (CIHR 2019). However, it is important to recognize that bias may already be present at the level of hypothesis formulation itself. Scientific inquiry is never fully neutral: the selection of research questions, assumptions about “typical” physiology, and interpretations of prior findings are shaped by historical, cultural, and often gendered norms (Schiebinger 2020). For instance, cardiovascular disease has long been studied with a male-centric model, under the assumption that symptoms, pathophysiology, and effective treatments are largely the same for both sexes. This led to the historical underdiagnosis of myocardial infarction in females, as their symptoms often differ (e.g., fatigue, nausea, shortness of breath) from the “classic” male-associated chest pain model (Heidari et al. 2016; Mehta et al. 2016). Consequently, hypotheses and diagnostic tools developed from male-biased models can systematically neglect sex-specific manifestations, leading to delayed diagnoses and suboptimal care in females. Incorporating a sex- and gender-sensitive lens already during hypothesis generation helps to challenge default assumptions and expand the scope of inquiry, ultimately increasing scientific rigor and societal relevance.

Next, plan to include samples (DNA, RNA, organelles, cells, tissues) isolated from both sexes and, in an in vivo study, animals of both sexes. Document sex for every sample and every patient/animal. If the sample size allows, disaggregate collected data by sex. Even if the study topic is not a sex difference in the phenomenon, the study should still include both sexes and preferably report data disaggregated by sex. In studies explicitly testing for sex differences, power analyses must be stratified by sex to ensure sufficient sensitivity to detect meaningful differences. This includes calculating sample sizes and minimum detectable effect sizes separately for each sex, as well as considering interaction effects between the sex and the primary variables of interest. Failure to do so risks both false negatives (due to underpowered subgroup analyses) and false positives (through overgeneralization). Moreover, sex-stratified power calculations are essential for transparency and reproducibility, and should be documented in protocols and reports. We are at the forefront of incorporating sex into biomedical research and there are opportunities for novel discoveries. In essence, the sex (and if applicable gender) variable is to be considered as a dimension throughout the scientific cycle (from the design and execution to the analysis and reporting – see Table 2) and also across different biological levels of resolution. In the next section we will highlight the differences on the molecular, cellular, tissue and the organism level that can arise from considering sex as a variable.

3.1. Impact of sex on the molecular level

Genetic and genome-wide sex differences have an impact on both the development of human disease and the patient outcomes. Due to the incomplete X chromosome inactivation, some genes can be expressed from both alleles in females, but not in males, which results in the sex bias based on the presence of sex chromosomes (Lopes-Ramos, Quackenbush, and DeMeo 2020). For example, reduced cancer incidence in females compared to males across a variety of tumor types has been attributed, in part, to the male-biased mutations in genes that escape X-inactivation (Dunford et al. 2017). Genes that escape X-inactivation associated with an advantage in anti-tumor response in females (for example FOXP3 (Chang et al. 2014) and CD40L (Sarmiento et al. 2019)) are also associated with increased susceptibility to autoimmune

disease in females.

Many cellular processes that show sex disparity – immune response, regulation of apoptosis and cell cycle, metabolism and DNA repair – are regulated by the p53, protein that has an extensive interaction network partly located on the X chromosome, where accessibility of chromatin is also dependent on sex (Liu 2020; Kukurba et al. 2016). In cancer, more than 60 individual genes and sex-biased molecular signatures comprising of more than a thousand of genes per signature have been identified (Yuan et al. 2016). In addition, more than 50 percent of clinically actionable genes showed sex-biased expression. Sex-biases existed in both coding and non-coding genes (Li et al. 2020), but the mechanisms behind these differences are yet to be elucidated.

Differences in methylation patterns of genes have also been observed between the two sexes, as well as sex differences in folding of the genome, activity and repair (Credendino, Neumayer, and Cantone 2020). Even though most transcription factors (proteins involved in the process of converting, or transcribing, DNA into RNA) are not differentially expressed between males and females, many have sex-biased regulatory targeting patterns (Lopes-Ramos et al. 2020). With the advancements in CRISPR-Cas9 technology that allows gene editing, sex of the edited cell has shown to be an important determinant, as more than 100 genes showed sex-bias in a CRISPR-Cas9 knockout screen (Guo and Xiong 2023). Therefore, even at the molecular level, one has to include and document the sex of the source of the biological material and, if adequate number of samples allows, perform sex-segregated analysis.

3.2. Impact of sex on the cellular level

At the cellular level, irrespective of the exposure to sex hormones, cells differ innately according to sex. Many cellular organelles show sex differences in function (such as endoplasmic reticulum, lysosomes and mitochondria (Ranjit et al. 2019; Shang et al. 2021)). For example, mitochondria – organelles that produce the majority of adenosine tri-phosphate (ATP) for optimal cell functioning and are implicated in several cardiovascular, neurological and metabolic diseases – are exclusively maternally inherited and their modulation can exert differential effects in males and females

(Ventura-Clapier et al. 2017). Male sensory neurons are more sensitive to mitochondrial stress than female neurons, making them more prone to injury (Maguire et al. 2022). *In vivo*, male and female cells in mice respond differently to stressors even before the production of fetal sex hormones, as early as 10.5 days post-conception before sexual differentiation (Penaloza et al. 2009).

Sex differences in stress response may have consequences in the course of the disease and response to therapy. For example, in humans the number of specific immune cell types in circulation differs between sexes: lymphocyte subsets including B cells (higher in females), CD4+ T cells (higher in females), CD8+ T cells (higher in males) and CD4/CD8 ratios (higher in females) are all well documented (Klein and Flanagan 2016). Around fifty genes that are involved in innate and adaptive immunity are on the X chromosome (Meester et al. 2020), and the difference in initiating an inflammatory immune response between the sexes translates into difference in immune defense against cancer and in incidence of autoimmune disorders (Haupt et al. 2021). Therefore, using cells derived from both sexes and segregated analyses are of utmost importance for modeling cancer and immune disorders on the cellular level.

However, outside of the body, in the *in vitro* conditions, sex differences in hormones, stressors, cytokines, nutrients and other contextual tissue signaling, are absent. *In vitro* models are especially important in elucidation of effects of the genetic sex and sex hormone signaling on a particular phenotype. One also must bear in mind that the additives used in the *in vitro* culture, like the calf or bovine serums that are added for better cell growth, are often a mixture of male and female serum, and can therefore contain both male and female sex hormones. Almost fifty years ago it was reported that levels of steroid hormones in sera can impact *in vitro* cell growth and cloning efficiencies, and that levels of progesterone higher than 1pg/L could inhibit proliferation (Milo et al. 1976). A study comparing adult bovine male serum (MS), female serum (FS), and castrated male serum (C-MS) effects on myogenic satellite cells, found that male steroid hormones in MS promoted myogenic differentiation to the greater extent, while FS induced the highest lipid accumulation and differentiation into adipocyte-like cells (Lee et al. 2011). In addition, phenol red, a dye used to monitor the pH of the culture media bears a structural resemblance to some nonsteroidal estrogens and stimulates the proliferation

of estrogen receptor-positive cells in a dose-dependent manner acting as a weak estrogen (Berthois, Katzenellenbogen, and Katzenellenbogen 1986).

Establishment of the equivalent cell lines from male and female inbred animal models is possible, but is not feasible from human biological material and adequate representation of males and females is not always possible. For example, given the heterogeneity of mutation profiles in cancer cells, one cannot oversimplify and compare female and male derived cell lines without taking in to account the driver mutations.

Depending on the scientific question, inclusion of cell types from both sexes in an adequate number can allow for sex-segregated analysis. The large number of cell lines needed to have an adequate sample size for well-powered analysis is the major obstacle in this kind of experimentation.

3.3. Impact of sex on the tissue model/organ on a chip level

In recent years, *ex vivo* tissue explants, organoids and organ-on-a-chip techniques have revolutionized biomedical research, as they use human material and, in part, humanely replace animal experimentation. These models mimic human tissues and organs and contain multiple cell types and extracellular components that help better modeling of the cell behavior. However, sex is rarely even documented in the description of models, and cells from different sources and sexes are used in combination. Gene expression analyses revealed that in addition to the reproductive organs and the breast tissue, the brain, heart, colon and thyroid are the most sexually dimorphic organs in the body (Gershoni and Pietrokovski 2017; Lopes-Ramos et al. 2020; Mayne et al. 2016). Apart from the cardiac tissue modeling, where engineered male and female cardiac tissues paralleled sexual dimorphism observed in the clinic, and were proposed to be used in screenings for sex differences in drug response prior to the clinical trials (Lock et al. 2022), little has been done in terms of development of sex-specific organ-on-a-chip models. Filling the knowledge gap on the sex differences in pathophysiology is critical for true precision medicine and also presents an excellent opportunity for novel discoveries.

3.4. Impact of sex on the animal research level

Advances in biomedicine strongly rely on research performed in mice and rats. Anatomical, physiological and genetic parallels with humans have made mice indispensable in preclinical research (Bryda 2013). Historically, more preclinical studies cumulatively have been performed in males. Some of the myths that propelled male-centric research, like the one that ovarian hormones make data from female animals more variable have since been debunked, as hormone fluctuations have impact on physiology and behavior in both males and females (Dalla et al. 2024) and are today considered as general biological variability and not sex-related variability (Levy et al. 2023). While in females estrogen and progesterone fluctuate in cycles, in males levels of testosterone can be up to five times higher in dominant versus subordinate mice (Machida, Yonezawa, and Noumura 1981).

Best practices for tracking hormone fluctuations in both male and female rodents, but also sex-specific behavioral readouts, can be found in a recent practical guide for inclusive preclinical neuropsychopharmacological research (Dalla et al. 2024). On the other hand, some researchers use only female mice for practical and financial reasons. Namely, male and female animals have to be housed separately, and while female mice are housed in groups and take up less of the housing space, depending on a mouse strain, male animals often have to be separated and housed individually due to the aggressive territorial behavior in groups. Most often, high cost of animal experiments is cited as a barrier for using both sexes. Keeping in mind the 3R rule of Russel and Burch (Russell 1992) that stand for Replacement (avoid the use of animals), Reduction (use fewer animals to obtain sufficient data, or maximize the information obtained per animal) and Refinement (minimize pain and distress, and enhance the welfare of an animal), including animals of both sexes at first looks as going against the Reduction rule. However, omission of females in preclinical studies has led to failure in translation in clinical trials, misdiagnosis and inappropriate therapies and neglect of fundamental biological principles (McCullough, McCarthy, and de Vries 2014). Given the inherent differences in the immune system, metabolism, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of drugs in males and females, any research aspiring to be translated

into therapy should include animals of both sexes and in addition to the 3R rule use the 4C rule: Consider, Collect, Characterize and Communicate sex as a biological variable (<https://orwh.od.nih.gov/sex-as-biological-variable>).

Interestingly, recent evidence suggests that the sex of the researcher may itself influence the physiological response of rodents: male olfactory cues—including those of human males—can induce a stress response and temporary analgesia in mice and rats. This raises the possibility that many preclinical findings may be systematically biased if the experimenters were predominantly male—a variable that is rarely recorded or reported (Sorge et al. 2014).

4. Can we incorporate gender into the experimental design

Gender is a socially constructed, dynamic, and multidimensional concept that encompasses roles, behaviors, identities, and power relations, shaped by historical and cultural contexts. Gender is inherently complex construct and cannot be appropriately modeled in basic and translational biomedical research in the same way as biological sex. However, defined aspects of gender —such as specific stress exposure, caregiving patterns, or access to resources—can be operationalized in animal studies through environmental manipulations, contextual variables, or behavioral proxies. In clinical and population-based human studies, gender should be actively integrated, using validated instruments (e.g., gender indices or role-based surveys) to capture its complexity beyond binary categories.

The impact of gender on health is substantial, affecting exposure to environmental risks, health behaviors, symptom reporting, and treatment adherence. It is therefore possible to simulate gender-related effects, for instance by introducing psychosocial stressors in experimental designs that also account for sex, or by disaggregating data along gender-relevant variables. However, researchers must be especially mindful of their own implicit gender assumptions, as stereotyped thinking can bias both study design and interpretation.

Concepts such as gender identity and gender modality add further nuance and have begun to enter biomedical and public health research, particularly in fields such as mental health, endocrinology, and transgender health (Ashley 2022; DuBois and

Shattuck-Heidorn 2021). Though rarely addressed in experimental biomedical models, their inclusion is gaining relevance in translational and clinical contexts.

5. Computational approaches

The limitation of a small sample or group size at any of the mentioned levels of incorporating sex as a variable (cell, tissue, animal) could be addressed with the emerging computational approaches. For example, machine learning algorithms can detect complex, non-linear sex-associated patterns in high-dimensional omics data, even with modest sample sizes, provided rigorous cross-validation and model interpretability measures are applied (Beam and Kohane 2018; Koprulu et al. 2025). Bayesian hierarchical modeling has been used to improve inference stability in sex-disaggregated biomedical data by incorporating prior biological knowledge and accounting for data uncertainty (Andrew Gelman 2013). Moreover, transfer of learning approaches could allow researchers to leverage existing data from related domains or populations to augment underpowered sex-specific analyses, as shown in multi-cohort gene expression studies (Taroni et al. 2019). While these techniques cannot replace careful study design and sampling, they are increasingly essential in exploratory analysis and hypothesis generation, particularly in sex-informed precision medicine.

Moreover, the rise of *in silico* approaches and systems biology opens new avenues for the integration of gender as a variable into biomedical research. Computational models and synthetic datasets allow the simulation of sociobehavioral influences on biological processes, offering a promising complement to traditional lab-based methods. These tools create opportunities to explore how gender-related variables may interact with biological sex to shape health outcomes—paving the way for more inclusive and predictive models of human biology (see Table 2 for further reading).

6. Conclusions and further resources

Increasing evidence demonstrates that considering sex as a biological variable is essential for improving the rigor, reproducibility, and translational relevance of biomedical

research (Regensteiner et al. 2025; Lee 2018; Miller et al. 2017; Bale and Epperson 2017; White et al. 2021; Vanden Noven et al. 2023). In scientific work we observe how an amalgam of effects of genetics, epigenetics, sex hormones, environment, behavior and lifestyle influences differences between sexes in disease development, progression and response to therapy. Currently, there are no policies that mandate universal inclusion of both sexes into basic and preclinical biomedical research. National Institute of Health (USA) introduced requirements for federally funded scientists to include both males and females in cell and animal studies starting in 2016, however in 2025 the NIH added a “Historic Document” label to webpages describing the Sex as Biological Variable policy — effectively archiving it as a past policy, along with removal of all gender related terminology. With this in mind it is ever more important to stimulate scientists to integrate sex and gender aspects into research, but we need a set of clear instructions on how to incorporate these as variables (Nieuwenhoven and Klinge 2010). Generation of universal practical guidelines and policies will be a cumbersome task and will need experts from various fields, with mandatory presence of study design experts, sex differences experts, and statisticians. One such guideline specific for neuropsychopharmacological research has recently been published (Dalla et al. 2024). Additionally, the Sex Inclusive Research Framework provides a practical approach to addressing these issues in preclinical research proposals (Karp et al. 2025).

Even though researchers often recognize the importance of incorporating these variables they fail to apply them to their own research. A study that followed the impact of a requirement of the Canadian Institutes of Health Research to indicate whether research designs accounted for sex or gender in proposed research found that biomedical researchers were the least likely to report accounting for sex and gender (Johnson et al. 2014). Most often, biomedical researchers rather than attempting to interpret the sex-specific effects, treat the sex as a confounding variable with an aim to filter it out. Science has built a legacy of excluding females, people of color and those from other historically marginalized groups from the scientific enterprise. We all have a role to play in addressing the problem of the sex bias and sex reporting omission. Scientists control the research design. If the information is available, it is always important to include information about sex, gender and race, as academic research has suffered from being reductionist and

biased towards males and whites/Caucasians (DuBois and Shattuck-Heidorn 2021). Ask yourself: does the topic of your research affect males and females differently and if so, could it be a consequence of a sex difference or gender difference? Design the study so that you collect and use genetic material, cells, tissues and animals of both sexes. Basic biological principles are common for both sexes but it is important to consider possible differences. Not every study needs to be designed to evaluate sex differences. However, the sex needs to be noted and reported, to allow for reproducibility and prevent generalization. European Union policy review on how inclusive analysis can improve research and innovation (Schiebinger 2020) suggests that all studies in humans and animals should consider whether sex is a covariate, confounder, or explanatory variable. Some have argued that including both sexes will slow down research and waste resources (Fields 2014), while the reality is that failed clinical trials that resulted from not taking sex into account in basic and translational research had higher effect when considering the resulting human and capital cost in misdiagnoses and inappropriate therapies for females (McCullough, McCarthy, and de Vries 2014). In an analysis of almost 2000 animal studies, a male bias was found in 8 out of 10 biological disciplines (Beery and Zucker 2011). In addition to being harmful, this lack of interest in sex differences also presents a missed opportunity for innovation (Heidari et al. 2016; Tannenbaum et al. 2019). Studying predominantly one sex contributes to the failure of translation of basic findings to the therapeutic benefit in the clinic along with the subjective bias, inappropriate experimental design and improper statistical analysis.

To support researchers in implementing these principles, we propose a practical guideline that summarizes key considerations for integrating sex and gender at each stage of the biomedical research process. This structured overview (see Table 2) translates conceptual insights into actionable steps—from hypothesis formulation to data reporting—aiming to improve the rigor, reproducibility, and inclusivity of biomedical research.

Research Stage	Considerations for Sex	Considerations for Gender	Resources / Tools / Literature
Hypothesis Formulation	Check for prior sex differences; avoid sex-blind assumptions	Reflect on gendered assumptions in question framing	Gendered Innovations 2 (EU, 2020) (Schiebinger 2020); CIHR Guidelines (2019) (CIHR 2019)
Study Design	Include both male and female organisms/cells; power analysis by sex	Plan for inclusion of gender-related variables (e.g., caregiving roles, stress exposure)	NIH SABV Policy (2016) (National Institutes of Health (U.S.) 2016); Dalla et al., 2024 (Dalla et al. 2024); SAGER Guidelines(Heidari et al. 2016; De Castro, Heidari, and Babor 2016);Rich-Edwards et al.2018 (Rich-Edwards et al. 2018)
Sample Collection	Document biological sex of all samples	Use validated gender measures in human studies	ORWH SABV Checklist; Reporting Templates (e.g. ARRIVE 2.0)(Percie du Sert et al. 2020)
Experimental Execution	Track sex-related variables	Minimize stereotype-driven bias in protocol design	Sorge et al., 2014 (Sorge et al. 2014); Mouse Estrous Tracking Tools
Data Analysis	Disaggregate data by sex; model interactions	Stratify or control for gender when possible; use social variables	Sex-disaggregated analysis protocols; R packages (e.g. 'emmeans' (R. 2025), 'afex'(Singmann H. 2024))
Interpretation	Interpret findings with biological sex in mind	Interpret effects in social context (e.g. norms, roles, power)	Gendered Innovations case studies (Schiebinger 2020); Fausto-Sterling, 2019 (Fausto-Sterling 2019)
Reporting	Report sex-specific findings even if not statistically significant	Use sex/gender-specific terminology consistently	SAGER Guidelines (Heidari et al. 2016; De Castro, Heidari, and Babor 2016); Nature editorial policies;

Table 2. Operationalizing Sex and Gender in Biomedical Research: A Stepwise Guide.

More useful resources on how to consider possible explanations for sex- and gender-related phenomena can be found on the Canadian Institutes of Health Research

website (<https://www.cihr-irsc.gc.ca/e/50836.html>) and in “Sex and Gender Equity in Research: rationale for the SAGER guidelines and recommended use” (Heidari et al. 2016).

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Ethical statement

This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors.

Informed consent

Article did not involve human participants or use of their data.

Author contributions

J.G. conceived the article and wrote the first draft. C.C and M.Z. revised the manuscript and provided critical feedback.

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